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THE APENNINE SIBYL

A MYSTERY AND A LEGEND

WORLD OF THE SIBYL: THE ITALIAN APENNINES AND THE SIBILLINI MOUNTAIN RANGE¹

1. A Sibyl in the Apennines

What is a "Sibyl"? In the classical world, Sibyls were women bestowed with the gift of prophecy. They actually spoke on behalf and with the words of a god. Inspired by Apollo, the Sibyl of Delphi chanted the visions that seized her when asked for oracular responses. In Cuma, near Naples, another Sibyl had passed the wisdom contained in her books on to a Roman king, Tarquinius.

Fig. 1 - Delphic Sibyl as painted by Michelangelo on the ceiling of the Sistine Chapel in Rome

¹ Articles released in year 2017
(http://www.italianwriter.it/TheApennineSibyl/TheApennineSibyl_SibylsApennine.asp)

The Sibyls were generally considered as priestesses of Cybele, the Phrygian goddess worshipped as a life-giving mother to the earth, amidst the precipitous slopes and ravines of the mountains. The answers they provided were cryptic and easily misunderstood, as men liked to catch of their words just what they craved for within their own soul.

Quoting from Varro, an ancient scholar whose work has gone lost, another renowned Latin author, Lactantius, reports that the Sibyls added up to ten. This is the classical list of Sibyls, including the Delphic, the Cumaean, the Tiburtine and others.

Early Christian writers, like Isidore of Seville, claimed that the Sibyls, pagans as they were, had anticipated the coming of Jesus on earth, by predicting the birth of the Son of God. That they would have achieved by using their foretelling faculties.

Yet something seems to be at variance with the classical list of oracular priestesses: in the fifteenth century, another Sibyl, apparently a new one, had made her appearance in a barren region of Central Italy.

That was the Apennine Sibyl. An enduring mystery whose spell is still alive in our present days.

2. The Sibyls who chanted the Incarnation

In early Christianity, the Sibyls – pagans as they were – were considered as witnesses of the Incarnation. Owing to their vaticinating powers, early-Christian authors reported that the Sibyls had divined the coming of the Son of God, before the actual birth of Jesus in Betlehem. Isidore of Seville, who lived between the sixth and seventh century, wrote in his *Etymologiae sive Originum* (Book VIII, Chapter 8) the following sentence about the Sibyls:

«Quarum omnium carmina efferuntur, in quibus de Deo et de Christo et gentibus multa scripsisse manifestissime conprobantur» («Songs by all of them are published in which they are attested to have written many things most clearly even for the pagans about God and Christ»).

Fig. 2 - The excerpt by Isidore of Seville on the Sibyls from an ancient edition of the *Etymologiae sive Originum*

And that's why the myth of the Sibyl has survived the coming of the new Christian era and the disappearance of the old gods: they were part of God's greater design for the salvation of the world.

In the fifth century A.D., Augustine of Hippo, the great theologian and philosopher, included the Sibyls in the Christian theological system, conferring further life to their legend for the centuries to come. In Book XVIII, Chapter XXIII of his *The City of God* he wrote the following statements about the Sibyls:

«Of the Erythræan Sibyl, Who is Known to Have Sung Many Things About Christ More Plainly Than the Other Sibyls

This sibyl of Erythræ certainly wrote some things concerning Christ which are quite manifest, and we first read them in the Latin tongue in verses of bad Latin, and unrhythmical, through the unskillfulness, as we afterwards learned, of some interpreter unknown to me. For Flaccianus, a very famous

man, who was also a proconsul, a man of most ready eloquence and much learning, when we were speaking about Christ, produced a Greek manuscript, saying that it was the prophecies of the Erythraean sibyl, in which he pointed out a certain passage which had the initial letters of the lines so arranged that these words could be read in them in Greek language "Jesus Christ the Son of God, the Saviour." [...]

But this sibyl, whether she is the Erythraean, or, as some rather believe, the Cumæan, in her whole poem, of which this is a very small portion, not only has nothing that can relate to the worship of the false or feigned gods, but rather speaks against them and their worshippers in such a way that we might even think she ought to be reckoned among those who belong to the city of God».

Fig. 3 - Augustine of Hippo, the quote on the Sibyl from his *The City of God*

[in the original Latin text] « Eodem tempore nonnulli Sibyllam Erythraeam vaticinatam ferunt. Sibyllas autem Varro prodit plures fuisse, non unam. Haec sane Erythraea Sibylla quaedam de Christo manifesta conscripsit; quod etiam nos prius in latina lingua versibus male latinis et non stantibus legimus per nescio cuius interpretis imperitiam, sicut post cognovimus. Nam vir clarissimus Flaccianus, qui etiam proconsul fuit, homo facillimae facundiae multaeque doctrinae, cum de Christo colloqueremur, graecum nobis codicem protulit, carmina esse dicens Sibyllae Erythraeae, ubi ostendit quodam loco in capitibus versuum ordinem litterarum ita se habentem, ut haec in eo verba legerentur: , quod est latine: Iesus Christus

Dei Filius Salvator. [...] Haec autem Sibylla sive Erythraea sive, ut quidam magis credunt, Cumaea ita nihil habet in toto carmine suo, cuius exigua ista particula est, quod ad deorum falsorum sive factorum cultum pertineat, quin immo ita etiam contra eos et contra cultores eorum loquitur, ut in eorum numero deputanda videatur, qui pertinent ad civitatem Dei».

3. *An Apennine Sibyl in a fifteenth-century chivalric romance*

In Andrea da Barberino's *Guerrino the Wretch* (*Guerrin Meschino* in Italian) is a fifteenth-century romance recording for the first time in history the presence of a sibilline oracle on a remote peak of the Sibillini Mountain Range, set in the Italian Apennines, with a description of the cave and its fairy inhabitants.

In Italy, the tale of knight Guerrino and his amazing adventures was known and familiar to everybody: storytellers used to narrate his deeds in public squares, at the corners of the streets, in village fairs and open-air markets, and during town festivals. People were enthralled by the description of the knight's bravery, and the depiction of the eerie cavern and magical kingdom hidden beneath the rocky crest. And the fame of the cave travelled far and fast.

As narrated by Andrea da Barberino in his romance, the main character Guerrino, a valiant knight, ascended the eerie mountain in the Apennine while engaged in a long and hazardous quest, in search of his lost parents. He had come to know that a Sibyl resided in a cave on the mountain-top, and he was determined to reach her abode and interrogate her on his parents' identity and whereabouts:

«the mountains where the Sibyl is found are in the middle of Italy, where strong winds blow for the mounts are high and there is the abode of griffins [...] so he went across the mountains of Aspromonte and travelled to the town of Norcia, which is in the midst of the great mountain of Apennine [...] And an elderly man, who had listened to their words, replied to him: "Sir, he said the truth, that a Sibyl actually dwells beneath our mountain fastnesses, for I remember that three young men came to this land: they went there, two of them came back and the other never returned"».

Fig. 4 - An excerpt from the chivalric romance *Guerrino The Wretch*

[In the original Italian text: «le montagne dove è la Sibilla è in mezo de Italia dove sono tuti venti per ché sono alte e za lì stavano li grifoni; e la più pressa città che li sia se chiama Norza [...] e passò le montagne de Asperamonte e vene a la città de Norza la qual è in mezo de la grande montagna d'pinino [...] Respose uno homo anticho che se fermò audire parlare e disse o gentilhomo lo è vero quello che dice costui e che la Sibilla è in questa nostra montagna per ché io me ricordo venire tre gioveni in questa terra: che ando[ro]no lì, doi tornono e l'altro non tornò mai»]

In the chivalric romance *Guerrino the Wretch*, a connection between the Apennine Sibyl and the Nativity is mentioned, with a peculiar overlapping between the pagan priestess and the Holy Mary. One of the men asked by Guerrino for information on the Sibyl so replies to him:

«I heard that the wise Sibyl was a virginal maid, so that she had hoped that God would enter into her when the Incarnation occurred in the Holy Mary. Because of that different choice she grieved and was then sentenced amid these mountainous ridges».

The Sibyl, a virgin like the Holy Mary, had aspired to be the chosen one to bear the Jesus in her womb. Yet, God's design was not hers: Mary was chosen and the Sibyl was punished for her overambitious wish and sent to a remote confinement among the Apeninnes.

Is that a reminiscence of the oracular role of the Sibyls, who had foretold the coming of Jesus on earth, as attested in the works by Isidor of Seville

and Augustine of Hippo? Maybe. Nonetheless, it is the same Apennine Sibyl who denies any connection to the Holy Mary, by choosing for herself a different lineage, as we will see later on.

4. The Apennines as an abode of the classical Sibyls

A Sibyl and the Apennines, a link that seems to become apparent, for the very first time, during the early fifteenth century, with a romance such as *Guerrino the Wretch*. Is there any evidence of this connection in earlier literary works?

Actually there are references to the Apennines as a suitable setting for Sibyls and their oracular powers. Mentions of this can be retrieved in earlier works, as we will show in the next paragraphs.

4.1 The Sibyl and the Apennines in a most precious manuscript dating to the twelfth century

It is not so widely known that the connection between a Sibyl and the Apennine range has not been established in the fifteenth century with *Guerrino the Wretch* and Antoine de La Sale: earlier links exist, and the one of them dates back to more than two centuries earlier, as is attested in the valuable manuscript n. 25407 residing in the Bibliothèque Nationale of France.

The manuscript contains *Le Livre de Sibile* (*The Book of the Sibyl*), an antique work attributed to Philippe de Thaon, an anglo-norman author of Middle-Age treatises on stones and animals.

In the account reported in *Le Livre de Sibile* (sheet 162), a tale is told about a hundred Roman senators who, during the same night, had the same inexplicable dream, featuring nine multi-coloured suns. The puzzled senators decided to summon the Tiburtine Sibyl to Rome and ask her the meaning of their dream.

Fig. 5 - *Le Livre de Sibille* in manuscript 25407 of the Bibliothèque Nationale of France

But the “regine Sibille” (Queen Sibyl, a title that is also widely used by Andrea da Barberino in his *Guerrino The Wretch*) refused to explain the dream right there in Rome, a place that was unclean; she invited the senators to move to another place more fit to the disclosure of an oracular response: in the anglo-norman text, “ki apenin anun”, all of them should move “to the apennines”.

Fig. 6 - An excerpt of *Le Livre de Sibille* where the Sibyl is bestowed the title of “Queen”

Thus, here is a first amazing connection between a Sibyl and the Apennines. It is a link established around year 1120. The Apennines, as a proper place for magic and prophecies.

Fig. 7 - The Apennine mentioned in *Le Livre de Sibile* as a suitable place for the Sibyl to render her oracular responses

4.2 An Apennine Sibyl from the early Middle Ages?

However, the anglo-norman chronicle from Philippe de Thaon (*Le Livre de Sibile*, XII century) is not the earliest mention of a Sibyl in the Apennines.

From the earliest centuries of Middle Ages and possibly ever since late Roman times, the Italian Apennines had been connected to Sibyls. Many manuscripts (e.g. Oxford Bodleian Library, manuscript Laud n. 633, XIII sec.), which report older versions of the “Prophecy of the Tiburtine Sibyl” in Latin, drawn from very ancient manuscripts now lost, speak clearly and plainly of the Apennine. Such older versions were collected in a later work, the “*Mirabilis Liber*” (1522), which states the following:

«The Sibyl replied to them: it is not convenient, in this unclean place and so polluted by conflicts, to unveil the sacred secrets of this dream. You rather come with me, I will climb the Apennine mount, and there I will foretell to you the fate of Roman citizens; and the Romans did what she had asked them to».

[In the original Latin text: «Respondens Sibila dixit ad eos: Non est equum in loco stercoribus pleno, et diversis certaminatationibus polluto, sacramentum huius visionis detegere. Sed venite ascendam in montem apennin, et ibi vobis pronuntiabo que ventura sunt civibus Romanis, et fecerunt, ut dixit»].

Fig. 8 - The *Mirabilis Liber* reporting the prophecy rendered by the Tiburtine Sibyl in the Apennine mountains

So the Tiburtine Sibyl had spoken to the Roman senators: there was a mount among the Apennines, a special place where she could prophesize conveniently.

Could that place be what we know today as “Mount Sibyl”?

5. The origin of the Apennine Sibyl: Cuma or Tivoli?

The Apennine Sibyl seems to have suddenly popped up in the fifteenth century, when she was mentioned for the first time ever in the romance *Guerrino the Wretch* and in De La Sale's *The Paradise of Queen Sibyl*. Did she appear from nothing? Or possibly, is she the heir of the classical Sibyls of the Roman age?

The latter might be the right answer, and we may find at least two different ancestors for the Sibyl of the Apennines: both are Sibyls, and both are Italian.

Fig. 9 - The possible lineage of the Apennine Sibyl, connecting the fifteenth-century oracle to the Cumaean Sibyl or the Tiburtine Sibyl

5.1 Did the Cumaean Sibyl flee to the Apennines?

A first lineage takes us back to the Cumaean Sibyl, the most illustrious Italian Sibyl in antiquity. Publius Vergilius Maro writes, in his *Aeneid*, that «Cumaea Sibylla - horrendas canit ambages antroque remugit - obscuris

vera involvens»: terrific riddles she yells, as she sings in her cave, the truth enshrouded in darkness. The Sibilline Books containing the Cumaean Sibyl's prophecies were carefully preserved in a shrine at the Capitoline Hill in Rome.

But why the Cumaean Sibyl should have fled from her famous cave in Cuma to a remote Apennine peak?

Ancient lore reports two different reasons. According to one legendary tradition, the Cumaean prophetess had been a teacher and tutor of the young Holy Mary: in this role she had entertained the idea to take the place of the maiden and become herself the mother of the Son of God. Because of her vile, haughty desire she had been punished and sentenced amid the cliffs of the Apennine.

When Guerrino the Wretch meets the Sibyl, he questions her on this very topic: «O much wise Sibyl, the Divine Grace accorded to you the favour of being the teacher of that virgin who was the mother of the Saviour in his human flesh; how it happened you insanely did not succeed in saving your soul owing to the affliction that overwhelmed you when the deity did not incarnate in your womb?»

But she stops him abruptly and replies angrily that «I was no teacher to our lady. Sir Guerrino, I see you are not so smart as I thought; who ever told you such piece of infomation?». And she continues: «I want you to know my name. I was called 'Cumaean' by the Romans for I was born in a town in the countryside whose name is Cuma: before I was sentenced to this place I lived in the world one thousand two hundred years. When Aeneas came to Italy, I led him through the nether world: and I was seven hundred years old at that time».

Despite all her irritated replies, the Sibyl admits she has been “sentenced” to the craggy fastnesses of the Apennines. If not with relation to the Holy Mary, the reason for that may also be found in the persecutions carried out by early-Christian followers against the Greek and Roman deities, whose temples and shrines were ravaged after the fourth century A.D. Ludovico Ariosto, the author of *Orlando Furioso*, refers to this very lore when he writes «the Cumæan Sibyl [...] who fled, in antiquity, to a Cavern in the territory of Norcia, placed on a mountain-top amidst a gloomy forest, from

the charming abode she used to live in at earlier times». A safe den, against the growing threat by the new emerging religion.

The Cumaean Sibyl and the Apennine Sibyl: we just saw that a close link existed between them, so much so that in ancient maps the Lakes of Pilatus, at the very core the Apennine Sibyl's kingdom, bore the same name as the Cumaean prophetess' magical lake: the Lake of Avernus.

Yet, this is not the only lineage up to an ancient Sibyl we can spot today. Another ancestral link does exist to another classical Italian Sibyl: the Tiburtine oracle.

5.2 A Tiburtine ancestor for the Apennine Sibyl?

Beside the Cumaean, there is another classical Sibyl as to whom a sort of connection to the Apennine Sibyl might be highlighted: the Tiburtine Sibyl.

The tiburtine oracle is included in the famous list of ten Sibyls reported by Latin author Lactantius in his *Divinae Institutiones*, as a quote from Varro: «the tenth of Tibur, by name Albunea, who is worshipped at Tibur as a goddess, near the banks of the river Aniene, in the depths of which her statue is said to have been found, holding in her hand a book».

In early-Christian times, the Tiburtine Sibyl was known for the prophecy and legend of the nine suns: a visionary dream made by a hundred Roman senators at the same time, which the Sibyl explained as a succession of historical ages from the Roman empire to the advent of Christianity, future wars and finally the end of the world. The legendary account was copied in dozens of manuscripts across Europe.

The peculiar aspect about this Sibyl is that she is linked to mountains and the Apennines: in some manuscripts reporting the prophecy of the Tiburtine oracle on the nine suns, she tells the senators that she will provide them with a response «in apenninum», on the Apennine mountains, considered as a sacred and unblemished place as opposed to corrupted Rome. This same indication is present in “Le Livre de Sibile” (The Book of the Sibyl), a thirteen-century anglo-norman work attributed to Philippe de Thaon,

which reports the same Tiburtine Sibyl's episode by saying that the senators should move «ki apenin anun». An old manuscripted French version of the same prophecy dating to 1300 states «alons en la montagne ancyene» ('let's move to the old mountain'). Finally, in the “Liber Mirabilis”, a sixteenth-century book containing a collection of prophecies, the Tiburtine Sibyl invites the Roman senators «in monte apennin».

Fig. 10 - Tiburtine Sibyl, Anna Bacherini Piattoli, 1750, Collezione Alessandro Marabottini, Palazzo Baldeschi, Perugia (Italy), and excerpts drawn from ancient books and manuscripts all mentioning the Apennines as the abode of the Tiburtine Sibyl

Could the Tiburtine Sibyl have chosen a remote Apennine peak as her oracular shrine of choice? Could all that refer to the cliff of Mount Sibyl?

The surmise is truly fascinating. However, we must stick to facts (at least literary ones) and there is no evidence of any direct connection between Mount Sibyl and the Apennines mentioned in the Tiburtine oracle's nine-sun legend.

Furthermore, we must consider the illuminating words that Servius Marius Honoratus, a fourth-century scholar, wrote in his *Commentary on Virgil's Aeneid*: «Albunea. [...] quia est in Tiburtinis altissimis montibus». It is clear that the “high mountains” where the Tiburtine (or Albunea) Sibyl used to live are plainly the mountainous ridges at Tivoli, near Rome: they are not

as high as Mount Sibyl, nonetheless they are fully impressive and picturesque, with ravines and waterfalls celebrated throughout the centuries by scores of artists and men of letters.

So, the Apennine Sibyl is not the Tiburtine one (if we want to explore a more promising connection, we will have to study the story of the Cumaean). And yet, there is no doubt that by this focus on the oracular Apennines we have shown that in antiquity those lofty mountainous ridges in Italy were considered as a pure and unblemished place: a convenient location for oracles and prophetic responses, as we will also see in the next paragraph.

5.3 The Tiburtine Sibyl and her relation to a picturesque mountain setting

We have seen that, in antiquity, the Tiburtine Sibyl was reputed to live amid “high mountains” and rendered her oracular responses in the “apennines”. However, this does not imply any direct link to the Apennine Sibyl.

As a matter of fact, and as attested in an excerpt from Servius Marius Honoratus, the Tiburtine Sibyl just had her shrine in Tibur (modern Tivoli): a place whose picturesque setting with waterfalls and ravines, encircled by high mountains, has beguiled not only ancient Roman, but also scores of Grand Tour travellers starting from the sixteenth century and as far as our contemporary era.

In the pictures below, you can see the Temple of the Tiburtine Sibyl as it appears today: the Aniene river plunges its rushing waters down into the precipice opening its jaws just below the shrine, in a sinister gorge called “Valley of Hell”; from there, the water has broken its way further down through a sheer wall of rock, and it is swallowed by a devilish crack where no living being would ever survive if thrown into it.

Fig. 11 - The shrine of the Tiburtine Sibyl at Tivoli, near Rome

Fig. 12 - Another view of the shrine of the Tiburtine Sibyl at Tivoli

In classical time, the vista was even more picturesque than today: the “Valley of Hell” was thoroughly flooded with large waterfalls and countless small rivulets oozing from innumerable crevices in the rock wall, like a sort of inhuman kingdom of natural powers (today, the new nineteenth-century waterfall has almost cancelled this liquid show).

Fig. 13 - The waterfall beneath the Tiburtine Sibyl's shrine at Tivoli in the centuries of the Grand Tour

«Quae forma beatis ante manus artemque locis!», writes Publius Papinius Statius in his work 'Silvae', containing a portrait of the place, «largius usquam indulsit Natura sibi. Nemora alta citatis incubere vadis: fallax responsat imago frondibus, et longas eadem fugit umbra per undas. Ipse Anien - miranda fides - infraque superque saxeus hic tumidam rabiem spumosaque ponit murmura, ceu placidi veritus turbare Vopisci Pieriosque dies et habentes carmina somnos» [How kindly the temper of the soil! How beautiful beyond human art the enchanted scene! Nowhere has Nature more lavishly spent her skill. Lofty woods lean over rushing waters; a false

image counterfeits the foliage, and the reflection dances unbroken over the long waves. Anio himself — marvellous to believe — though full of boulders below and above, here silences his swollen rage and foamy din, as if afraid to disturb the Pierian days and music-haunted slumbers of tranquil Vopiscus].

That's why the Tiburtine Sibyl was considered as a “mountain”, “apennine” Sibyl. But this had nothing to do with the Apennine Sibyl, hidden in her den in the Sibillini Range area, a very different mountain and natural setting.

6. An oracle in the Apennines: the “*Historia Augusta*”

In our effort to trace back the origin of the Apennine Sibyl, we cannot miss a well-known excerpt drawn from the *Historia Augusta*, an antique collection of biographies of Roman Emperors written in the fourth century.

For the first time ever, I will show here the full text of the excerpt, with pictures of the *Historia Augusta*'s oldest manuscript (ninth century), written in a beautiful carolingian script.

Fig. 14 - The manuscript of the *Historia Augusta*, with superimposed a statue of Emperor Claudius II Gothicus

In the section “Divus Claudius” (deified Claudius) written by Latin author Trebellio Pollio and dedicated to Claudius II Gothicus, a soldier of barbarian origin who was proclaimed Emperor by his legions in 268 A.D., we found another important link to an oracle set in the Apennines.

After having asked an oracular response about the fortunes of his lineage in Comagena, a Roman outpost at the frontier with the Noricum (Danube region), Emperor Claudius moves to another oracle. Here is how the excerpt narrates the full story:

«Similarly, when once in the Apennines he asked about his own future, he received the following reply: "Three times only shall summer behold him a ruler in Latium". Likewise, when he asked about his descendants: "Neither a goal nor a limit will I set for their power". Likewise, when he asked about his brother Quintillus, whom he was planning to make his associate in the imperial power, the reply was: "Fate shall display him to people on earth not for long"».

Fig. 15 - The excerpt from the *Historia Augusta* mentioning an oracle in the Apennines

(In the original Latin text: «Item cum in Appennino de se consuleret, responsum huius modi accepit: "Tertia dum latio regnantem viderit aestas".

Item cum de posteris suis: "His ego nec metas rerum nec tempora ponam". Item cum de fratre Quintillo, quem consortem habere volebat imperii, responsum est: "Ostendent terris hunc tantum fata"»).

Once again, we have an oracle who delivers his/her prophecies amid the rugged peaks of the Apennines (the last prophetic statement is a verse from Vergilius' *Aeneid*). For Romans, Italy's mountainous backbone appears to be a special place, as we have already seen for the Tiburtine Sibyl, who in the legend of the nine suns tells the senators to move with her to the Apennines so as to render her oracular response in a fit, unblemished location.

Has the story of Claudius II Gothicus anything to do with the Apennine Sibyl? Nobody knows: the text provides no further clues, and it might just convey a reference - for instance - to the Tiburtine Sibyl. Yet, it is undeniable that the ancient tale found in the *Historia Augusta* is a confirmation of the fact that the Apennines were a magical place. A most convenient abode for a Sibyl of the Apennines.

7. The ritual vigil of a Roman Emperor: Suetonius and the Apennines

We have shown in previous paragraphs that the Apennines in Italy have something to do with classical Sibyls (Cumaeian, Tiburtine) and oracular shrines (*Historia Augusta*). We can even retrieve a further quote which goes in that same direction: a quote from first-century Latin writer Suetonius, the author of the celebrated work *The Twelve Caesars*.

Let's fly through the pages of the most ancient known manuscript handing down to us Suetonius' stories about twelve Roman emperors: it is preserved at the Bibliothèque Nationale de France in Paris, under the registration number "Lat 6115", a treasure coming down straight from the ninth century (see pictures). In his work, Suetonius recounts the life and deeds of Aulus Vitellius Germanicus Augustus, who reigned as an Emperor after the short-lived Galba and Otho: his rule lasted for nine months only to the end of 69 A.D. when he was slain by partisans of Vespasian.

Fig. 16 - The section about Vitellius in Suetonius' *The Twelve Caesars*

Aulus Vitellius was a descendant of a «stirpem ex Sabinis», a family originating from the province of Sabina, in central Italy, sitting right on the Apennines. And he probably knew well that this mountainous chain was a peculiar place.

When his legions defeated his rival-Emperor Otho, who finally committed suicide by stabbing himself with a knife, he actually selected the Apennines for a special night of revelling and celebration. In Suetonius' words:

«He openly drained a great draught of unmixed wine and distributed some among the troops. With equal bad taste and arrogance, gazing upon the stone inscribed to the memory of Otho, he declared that he deserved such a Mausoleum, and sent the dagger with which his rival had killed himself to the Colony of Agrippina, to be dedicated to Mars. He also held a ritual vigil throughout the night on the heights of the Apennines. Finally he entered the city (Rome) to the sound of the trumpet, wearing a general's mantle and a sword at his side...».

(in the original Latin text: «plurimum meri propalam hausit passimque divisit. Pari vanitate atque insolentia lapidem memoriae Othonis inscriptum

intuens, dignum eo Mausoleo ait, pugionemque, quo is se occiderat, in Agrippinensem coloniam misit Marti dedicandum. In Appennini quidem iugis etiam pervigilium egit. Urbem denique ad classicum introiit paludatus ferroque succinctus...»).

Fig. 17 - The Apennines as mentioned in Suetonius' *The Twelve Caesars*

According to Suetonius, Aulus Vitellius left Gaul and, in his course to Rome to be acclaimed as the new victorious Emperor, he stopped one full night with his troops amid the Apennines - his ancestral homeland - for a sacred festival, a sort of thanksgiving to the divine favor.

Again, for ancient Romans the Apennines seemed to be a special place for rites and celebrations. Which mount or valley did Aulus Vitellius exactly select to carry out his vigil? Nobody knows. But sure enough the Apennines had a special attractiveness for oracles, shrines and ritual, devotional practices. The Apennine Sibyl was about to come.

8. In the name of the Sibillini: the "Tetrica rupes"

After having considered the role of the Apennines in the sibilline tradition, let's consider a specific portion of it, whose name bears the veritable stamp of a Sibyl: the Sibillini Mountain Range.

Today, 'Sibillini Mountain Range' in Italy is a well-known name, describing a territory sitting between the provinces of Umbria and Marche, where the magnificence of nature harbours a number of mysterious legends. But what was the name of the Sibillini in ancient times?

Fig. 18 - Landscapes in the Sibillini Mountain Range fully convey the impression of a magical place, suspended in time and history

Romans used to call the region “gloomy, frightful mountain” ('Tetrica rupes' in Latin), as mentioned by Vergilius in Book VII of his poem *Aeneid*, when describing the Italian troops that were being sent against Aeneas:

«Ecce Sabinorum prisco de sanguine magnum Agmen [...] postquam in partem data Roma Sabinis [...] qui Tetricae horrentis rupes [...] quos frigida misit Nursia»

(«Here comes the great Army of the ancient lineage of the Sabines [...] after Sabines were given a part of Rome [...] those who live at the dreadful Tetricus cliff [...] and those who come from cold, wintry Norcia»)

Fig. 19 - The excerpt from Vergilius' Aeneid containing the sentence on the "Tetricae horrentis rupes" - British Library, manuscript Harley n. 2772, eleventh century

Servius Marius Honoratus, a fifth century scholar, provides his own comment to the above line by Vergilius (*Commentarii in Vergilii Aeneidos libros*, Book VII), by specifying that «the Tetricus mountain is a barren, towering mountain, where stern men are said 'tetricos', sullen and gloomy»: «Tetricus mons in Sabinis asperrimus, unde tristes homines tetricos dicimus».

And Isidore of Seville, in Book X of his *Etymologiarum sive Originum* (sixth century A.D.), adds to Servius' text the following additional remark on the men living at the Tetricus: «inclined to silence, persistently taciturn» («Taciturnus, in tacendo diuturnus»).

The same name 'Tetricus' for the Sibillini Range is also mentioned by Silius Italicus, a Roman consul and poet who lived in the first century A.D. In his work *Punica* (Book VIII), he lists the Italian warriors summoned by the Romans to confront Hannibal at the Battle of Cannae (216 B.C.):

«Hunc Foruli magnaue Reate dicatum Caelicolum Matri necnon habitata pruinis Nursia et a Tetrica comitantur rupe cohortes»

(«With him come the soldiers of [...] Reate sacred to the great Mother of the Gods, and Nursia the abode of snow, and warriors from the Tetricus cliff»).

Furthermore, Marcus Terentius Varro, in Book II of his *De re rustica* (first century B.C.), writes that «even now there are several species of wild cattle in various places. [...] For there are many wild goats in Italy in the vicinity of Mount Fiscellum and Mount Tetrica» («Etiam nunc in locis multis genere pecudum ferarum sunt aliquot. [...] Sunt enim in Italia circum Fiscellum et Tetricam montes multae»).

But what does Varro mean by 'Mount Fiscellum'? The answer is in Pliny the Elder, who in his *Naturalis Historia* (Book III) states that «Velinos accolunt lacus [...] Nar amnis exhaurit illos sulphureis aquis Tiberim ex his petens, replet e monte Fiscello Avens iuxta Vacunae nemora et Reate in eosdem conditus» («in the vicinity of the Lakes of the Velinus [...] the Nar, with its sulphureous waters, exhausts these lakes running towards the Tiber; the river Avens flows from Mount Fiscellus near the groves of Vacuna and Rieti»).

So Pliny, in the above excerpt - which is most probably corrupt - seems to confuse the River Nera (which actually originates in the Sibillini Range) with the River Velino ('Avens'), flowing in and out the Lake of Piediluco, and whose source is found in the area of Mount Terminillo, together with a number of sulphurous springs. Thus the 'Fiscellus Mons' should be better identified with Mount Terminillo.

'Tetrica rupes', gloomy, frightful mountains: such was the name of the Sibillini Mountain Range in antiquity. And - as we will see in a subsequent paragraph - its name will later turn into something different and mysterious: a straight, unequivocal "Mount Sibyl".

9. In the name of the Sibillini: the Sibyl's Mountains

We don't know why, we don't know when, yet at a certain point in time across the centuries the "Tetrica rupes" (the name of the Sibillini Range in antiquity) seems to turn into something different: the whole mountainous fastness becomes "The Sibyl's Mountains".

In Chapter 137 of the fifteenth-century romance *Guerrino the Wretch*, the hero is told that the Sibyl «was to be found amid the mountains of the Apennine in the middle of Italy high up a town called Norza, some say it is called Norsia» («li iera in li monti de pinino i[n] lo mezo de Italia sopra una città chiamata Norza, alcuni dicono como la è chiamata Norsia»); only a few lines ahead, Guerrino asks people «on where is located the Sibyl's mount» («dove era il monte de la Sibilla»). Antoine de La Sale, at the very beginning of his *The Paradise of Queen Sibyl*, reports of a «mount of Queen Sibyl's lake» («mont du lac de la royne Sibille» - today's Mount Vettore) and a «mount of Queen Sibyl» («mont de la royne Sibille»), facing the former.

So, in the fifteenth century no reference to a “Mount Tetricus” can be traced anymore: the Sibillini Range, a portion of the Italian Apennines, is already identified as a mount or group of mounts related to a Sibyl. In addition, no reference to the peak we know today as Mount Vettore can be found at this late Medieval age.

If we jump further ahead in time, we find another clue dating back to 1566: it's the astounding map contained in Vatican manuscript n. 5241, where the whole mountainous massif is referred to with the following sentence: «this mount is called the 'chiavetoie' (Vettore?), also known as The Mountain of the Sibyl» («questa montagna dicono de chiavetoie, altramente La montagna della Sibilla»). Again, no “Tetrica rupes” is present anymore: the drawing shows a mountain range named “of the Sibyl” as a whole; and a first, early reference to something that might be our modern Mount Vettore is now present.

Fig. 20 - Vatican manuscript n. Lat 5241 including a map of the Sibillini Mountain Range

In the subsequent century, Father Fortunato Ciucci, a monk residing in Norcia, concentrates his attention on Mount Vettore. In his *Chronicles of the antique town of Norsia*, written in 1650, he clearly mentioned the «great Mount Vettore [...] its name is Victor owing to his being the greatest, and the best as to magnificence and other qualities» (il «gran Monte Vittore [...] si chiama Vittore per essere di tutti il maggiore, così egli l'istessa qualità ritiene in bellezza ed altre prerogative»). He does not mention a specific mount for the Sibyl, as he rather says that «on the very same Mount Vettore a ghastly Cavern opens its mouth where [...] a mendacious Sibyl has her abode» («nell'Istesso Monte Vittore s'apre un'orrenda Spelonca dove [...] abita una mensogniera Sibilla»).

Nonetheless, in the sixteenth and seventeenth centuries all the maps of the region show an isolated Mount Sibyl only, with no reference to a Mount Vettore nearby, nor to any larger massif surrounding the renowned peak.

Fig. 21 - The magical setting of the Sibillini Mountain Range

To come full circle, we must get as far as year 1869, when a local scholar, Feliciano Patrizi-Forti, writes his *On the Historical Essays about Norcia*. And here is what he states at page one of his seven-hundred-page work:

«The Apennine massif at whose base Norcia was founded is called 'Mount Sibyl', or 'Mons Tetricus' in antiquity» («Il gruppo appenninico alle falde del quale fu Norcia fondata, è detto 'Monte della Sibilla', anticamente 'Mons Tetricus'»).

In a single sentence, we find the whole transmutation path from the “Tetrica rupes” of the Romans to our modern “Sibillini Range”.

Somewhere along the way, a Sibyl has magically appeared, giving her legendary name to a whole Italian mountainous region: an amazing occurrence that still needs to undergo further investigation and research.

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